

Varben (ctDNA, remove duplicates then simulate)

Batch

A	1
B	2
C	3
D	4
E	5
F	6
G	7
H	8
I	9
J	10
K	11
L	12

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

Varben (ctDNA, remove duplicates then simulate)

Varben (ctDNA, remove duplicates then simulate)

